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Summary

Decompression sickness (DCS) remains a major problem of diving. Prevention of DCS is possible if the responsible physical events are understood and avoided. At the Naval Medical Research Institute (NMRI), a research program is addressing the problem by asking the questions: how much, where and how fast does gas enter the body, and how do bubbles originate and lead to symptoms? The answers, appropriately integrated, should provide substantial improvement in diving safety and efficiency.

Direct, manned penetration of the oceans depends upon man's ability to accommodate to this new environment, and to travel safely to and from the desired ocean depth. For more than 100 years, the process of returning to land pressure from increased ocean pressure, or decompression, has been observed to result often in a wide variety of symptoms. These vary from mild joint pain and skin rashes to sensory and motor loss, and even death. Collectively, these symptoms are referred to as decompression sickness or DCS. Through a combination of fundamental theory and crude experimentation, practices of a slow return to lower pressure have evolved. These procedures, called decompression tables, have reduced the severity of most cases of DCS and have reduced the incidence of symptoms to about 1% of the exposures that require use of the tables.¹ That incidence approaches an acceptable level of risk in some operations, but many of the newer procedures have a risk near 20%. The problem is of sufficient magnitude for the Navy to support a biomedical research program in decompression, now performed largely at NMRI and NEDU.

Prevention of decompression sickness requires avoiding the conditions that precipitate the symptoms. DCS is commonly thought to result from excess inert gas breathed by the diver while at ocean pressure. The gas in the diver's body can then form bubbles if the external pressure is released too fast for the gas to be eliminated normally. The disease can thus be prevented if the specified rate of pressure reduction is matched to the actual rate of gas elimination in a way that prevents bubble formation and/or growth. This simple word picture, however, must be elaborated by a number of assumptions and specific formulations that rest on tenuous grounds. At NMRI, we have recently started a systematic program of theory and experimentation to formulate rational decompression schedules. The program is structured around a series of fundamental questions that link reduction of pressure to human disease. Roughly in order of increasing complexity these questions are:

1. How much of a diver's breathing gas can dissolve in a human body? The answer to such a question is a quantity known as the solubility coefficient, the ratio of inert gas dissolved in a body tissue to the quantity of inert gas that remains in a gas phase. Handbooks of biochemistry and physiology tabulate solubility data, but information is scanty for gases and human body locations of interest to diving. We recently reviewed all published measurements of gas solubility and found

only a few studies of direct bearing to our question.² A current project is the development of an apparatus to measure solubility in small animal and human tissue samples. That device will be constructed to operate at the higher ambient pressure anticipated for human diving. The research should soon provide data on nitrogen and helium solubility in the body tissues associated with decompression symptoms.

In lieu of data, some theoretical predictions about solubility have been made. Unfortunately, the most common theory implies that all biological substances can be considered arbitrary linear combinations of water and olive oil. That viewpoint has not been developed because the related predictions lie only within several hundred percent of those in the few studies that have been reported. A new collaborative effort between NMRI and other Navy and civilian chemists is approaching the prediction of solubility by modern physical chemistry theories.³

2. Where does the excess gas exist in the body? Previous answers have invoked speculations of "water-like" and "oil-like" regions, without attempting to locate these anatomic regions. A few studies of gas distribution in specific anatomic sites can be found in biomedical studies of blood flow and anesthesia, but these areas are not of most interest to human diving. We have used modern radiotracer techniques to examine the distribution of labeled xenon gas in many areas of live dogs.⁴ These studies have demonstrated that skeletal joints (a common site of DCS symptoms) have a relatively high concentration and slow exchange of that gas. We are currently performing a similar study using a more interesting gas (nitrogen) in a more interesting species (human diver).⁵ Progress in that study is slowed by the extremely complex instruments required to produce and measure radionitrogen (¹³N). Already, however, we have demonstrated a markedly slow exchange of nitrogen in divers' knees.

3. How fast does gas enter and leave the body? Again, answers are available from both theoretical and experimental viewpoints. Traditional theory states that exchange follows a monoexponential curve whose time constant depends only on blood flow and gas solubility. In examining a number of theoretical possibilities for local gas exchange in tissue, we have concluded that the diffusion of gas should be very important as well. In fact, diffusion can affect the choice of gas for decompression safety.⁶ Several theoretical alternatives allow divergent predictions of which of a possible pair of divers' gases will be of most benefit.⁷

Experimental approaches for determining the exchange rates of inert gases have been published over several years. Most of these, however, are not useful for characterization of gases for decompression purposes. Our approach in this area was to first develop a mathematical formalism that allows

comparison of many experiments of varying conditions.⁸ That methodology was then applied to simultaneous study of thousands of sites in a dog.⁴ A product of that work was the first set of "maps" of gas exchange rates in a single animal. Equivalent maps of nitrogen exchange in humans is the goal of a current experiment.

4. How do gas bubbles form and grow? Presently, available theories suggest that bubble symptoms originate with: bubble formation, bubble volume, bubble number or bubble internal pressure.⁶ These theories have all been developed to explain simple decompression observations. At NMRI, we are engaged in developing quantitatively comparative methods to differentiate between theoretical predictions. One product of that thrust is the re-examination of homogeneous nucleation of bubbles in biological systems.⁹ The short-term goal of comparative bubble analysis is the design of animal decompression experiments to yield maximum information. A longer-term goal of measuring specifically bubble kinetics in animals and humans awaits refinement of ultrasonic instruments.

5. How do the bubbles produce symptoms? This question addresses the link between physics and pathology. Previously published reports addressing this question have been highly speculative and have cited numerous aspects of bubble behavior that are not available for direct study. Candidate explanations include mechanical blockage of blood vessels, biochemical processes initiated at the gas-tissue interface, and perhaps numerous indirect mechanisms as well.¹⁰ Studies at NMRI using physiological and pathological techniques are piecing together the sequence of decompression-induced events in several specific target organs: brain, spinal cord, lungs and heart. The other important tissue type is the skeletal joint, an area not under study now. More details of this aspect of NMRI's work can be found in other papers in the OCEANS'83 volume.

6. Can the above answers be integrated into practical guidelines? Previous attempts at systematic integration have been rare, and have typically floundered at the stage of human trials. A major problem has been failure to recognize the intrinsic variability of response among individuals. The animal work at NMRI accepted this variability and allowed design of experiments using statistical techniques.¹¹ Recently these techniques have been extended to allow systematic comparison of overall decompression theories and experiments of actual outcome (binary). The first successful application of this principle of maximum likelihood was in combining several hundred observations of helium saturation decompression in humans and evaluating the relative merits of several possible measures of risk.¹² This will be extended shortly to include statistical descriptions of gas exchange kinetics as well. Consideration of the probability of decompression sickness allows quantitative prediction of levels of expected risk, and can be used for practical guidance in the design of human decompression trials. The first of such trials is now underway at NMRI.

This report outlines the involvement of this laboratory in most of the important features of human DCS. Each of the studies has a specific importance in the final product of an overall algorithm to predict decompression and for application to any desired type of decompression table. The next generation of

decompression tables should therefore have two major improvements. First, the theoretical basis will consist of assumptions closely tied to experimental and theoretical physiology. Secondly, the tables will incorporate the cumulative body of human diving experience in a systematically quantitative format. These improvements should provide a significant advance in diving safety and efficiency.

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